

1 Quo vadis Map-based Search?

2 **Krzysztof Janowicz**¹ ✉

3 Department of Geography and Regional Research, University of Vienna, Austria

4 **Meilin Shi** ✉

5 Department of Geography and Regional Research, University of Vienna, Austria

6 **Zilong Liu** ✉

7 Department of Geography and Regional Research, University of Vienna, Austria

8 **Noemi Beluli** ✉

9 Department of Geography and Regional Research, University of Vienna, Austria

10 **Glenys Laetitia Bischoff** ✉

11 Department of Geography and Regional Research, University of Vienna, Austria

12 **Laura Marlene Huber** ✉

13 Department of Geography and Regional Research, University of Vienna, Austria

14 **Paul Huber** ✉

15 Department of Geography and Regional Research, University of Vienna, Austria

16 **Moritz Imrecke** ✉

17 Department of Geography and Regional Research, University of Vienna, Austria

18 **Manuel Kastner** ✉

19 Department of Geography and Regional Research, University of Vienna, Austria

20 **Dominik Knabe** ✉

21 Department of Geography and Regional Research, University of Vienna, Austria

22 **Franziska König** ✉

23 Department of Geography and Regional Research, University of Vienna, Austria

24 **Rainhard Neuhauser** ✉

25 Department of Geography and Regional Research, University of Vienna, Austria

26 **Niklas Neustätter** ✉

27 Department of Geography and Regional Research, University of Vienna, Austria

28 **Selina Stephanie Straßburger** ✉

29 Department of Geography and Regional Research, University of Vienna, Austria

30 **Stefan Karl Thurnhofer** ✉

31 Department of Geography and Regional Research, University of Vienna, Austria

32 **Florian Mathias Venier** ✉

33 Department of Geography and Regional Research, University of Vienna, Austria

34 **Laura Welz** ✉

35 Department of Geography and Regional Research, University of Vienna, Austria

36 — Abstract —

37 Maps and web search seem like a match made in heaven. Since at least 2005, many increasingly
38 sophisticated digital maps have been deployed on a wide range of web portals, whether for real
39 estate search, POI recommendations, neighborhood safety, or tourism. Interestingly, this trend
40 may be coming to an end or even reverse itself, with maps being either demoted or disappearing
41 altogether. Several potential reasons exist for this, including the rise of contextual information, the
42 size of mobile displays, commercial interests, and privacy concerns. While it is difficult to identify

¹ Corresponding author

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43 the drivers on a per-portal basis, documenting and categorizing this trend, e.g., to tell apart legal
44 reasons from commercial interests, is important to better understand the future of web-scale spatial
45 information visualization.

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47 tion systems → Web searching and information discovery; Information systems → Web interfaces

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51 **1 Motivation**

52 This is hard to admit, but we often do not understand the results shown on web maps, and
53 neither may you. For instance, if a booking platform shows five available hotels at a tourist
54 destination, we expect that there are five locations to choose from, and later discovering
55 that there are ten or more does not meet our intuition. Similarly, if an area nearby shows
56 no Points of Interest (POI), say restaurants, while areas further away do, intuitively, we
57 believe that there are no restaurants nearby. If we select Italy as our destination, we do not
58 expect to see vacation rentals from Austria or Croatia. Finally, if we type in a place name
59 into a search engine, in one case, we may receive an interactive web map in return, while in
60 another, we merely receive a static image of that same map; why?

61 While there are technical reasons for some of these results, e.g., hidden grids underlying
62 map search, or recommender systems extracting contextual information about our (inferred)
63 implicit needs in the background, there are also other drivers often leading to what we will
64 call *dark patterns* in web map design later. In fact, several current trends de-emphasize
65 maps or even replace them entirely with lists and AI-based chat interfaces. To some degree,
66 this reverses the development of past decade(s), namely maps and location-based search
67 going hand in hand, and where new, more sophisticated features are being added to improve
68 geographic information retrieval (GIR) and location-based services (LBS) in general.

69 This matters for multiple reasons: **(1)** current trends may reduce the quality of the
70 search, **(2)** may reduce the transparency of the results being presented, **(3)** design may be
71 driven by technological trends, not user needs, and, **(4)** finally, it may point to an interesting
72 (research) gap in spatial information visualization where our methods seem not to match the
73 needs of services and/or their customers.

74 Today, millions of maps are used on the web for many different purposes. Making general
75 statements about their capabilities and future development is out of the scope for this short
76 paper. Similarly, misleading or even lying with maps is as old as maps themselves and
77 has been subject to scientific studies for many decades [11]. Hence, we restrict ourselves
78 here to selected examples from three different use cases, namely **(1)** travel portals offering
79 accommodations and short-term stays, **(2)** POI recommendation services, **(3)** real estate
80 portals, and close with a few examples of **(4)** broader map-based web search, e.g., for
81 navigation or exploration. By *map-based web search*, we mean web-centric user interfaces for
82 portals that have (or used to have) a map widget as a central component of their search. We
83 thereby exclude services such as Google Earth, location-based games, mobile applications for
84 navigation, weather forecasting services, and so on. Finally, while the production and usage
85 of digital maps have been studied from many perspectives and using various technologies,
86 e.g., eye-tracking, we will focus on *changes* in how maps are deployed and which features

87 they offer. **More concretely, we aim at addressing the following research questions:**

- 88 ■ **RQ1:** What are the potential drivers that contribute to abrupt changes (e.g., decline) in
89 map-based web search?
- 90 ■ **RQ2:** To what extent does today’s map-based web search meet a naive user’s intuition?

91 The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. In Section 2, we highlight related
92 work to help put our work in perspective. Next, in Section 3, we describe our setup to survey
93 various web portals that offer map widgets. Section 4 discusses the results by example, puts
94 them into the perspective of current trends, e.g., chatbots, and discusses the potential future
95 of maps. Finally, Section 5 summarizes key points and provides directions for future work.

96 **2 Related Work**

97 Eye-tracking has proven to be effective in analyzing how people interact with maps, aiding
98 navigation, and assessing cognitive load, e.g., via measuring pupil diameter during various
99 map-related tasks [6, 9, 10]. While these technologies offer a promising avenue for our future
100 work, our focus here is on the *changing nature of map widgets on web portals*, e.g., why
101 features are being removed and how design decisions are increasingly driven by technology
102 and business models.

103 Utilizing booking platforms can facilitate the decision-making process in finding a suitable
104 listing. Given that the number of relevant options often exceeds the available search time of
105 a user, curated search results can reduce transaction costs associated with the search process.
106 Fradkin [4] examined Airbnb’s strategy to increase successful matches between hosts and
107 users. The study reveals that the result ranking is tailored to enhancing match rates by
108 predicting user behavior and host preferences. It is worth noting that more than 50% of the
109 users utilize the provided map, emphasizing the importance of map-based search results and
110 the visualization of geographic locations.

111 Content suggestions such as the display of landmarks and branded businesses on mobile
112 maps play an important role in shaping the geographic knowledge of users. Dalton and
113 Thatcher [3] demonstrated how this perception is profoundly influenced by the interests
114 of map providers (e.g., Google Maps and Apple Maps) through a wayfinding experiment
115 involving the use of landmarks as navigational descriptions. Using POI landmarks for
116 turn-by-turn directions not only facilitated more effective wayfinding but also served as a
117 form of advertising. According to the study, prominently placing a branded business such
118 as Starbucks on a map can leave a lasting impression on the perception of a user about
119 geographic space, particularly when it resonates with personal experiences.

120 The relationship between society and geo-technology has also been actively studied before.
121 For example, [12] revisited Microsoft’s “Pedestrian Route Production patent”, known as
122 the ‘avoid ghetto GPS’ to point to concerns arise regarding potential discrimination if the
123 patent’s concept of routing users away from ‘dangerous’ neighborhoods would indeed be
124 implemented, particularly when utilizing crime statistics and intransparent demographics.

125 The visual appearance of a map influences its perceived trustworthiness [5]. This trust-
126 worthiness is shaped by cultural backgrounds, as countries and companies may adopt their
127 own styles. For example, familiar map layouts are often perceived as more reliable, and they
128 are more likely to influence decisions and public perception [5].

129 One topic we would like to include, as mentioned in the introduction, are dark (design)
130 patterns. They are prevalent in various contexts, such as privacy settings, online gaming,
131 and online shopping. There is no well-agreed definition for dark patterns in maps but dark

132 patterns as such have been studied in interface design [7]. In the past, legislators and
 133 regulatory bodies have responded by enacting laws and regulations to restrict or prohibit
 134 certain dark patterns, highlighting their impact on user experience and digital ethics [1].

135 **3** Survey Setup

136 As technology evolves, one would expect digital maps to become easier to use, integrate
 137 more features, and provide more relevant information. However, recently, we have observed
 138 a contrary trend. We aim to address two questions in this section: (1) What accounts for
 139 this phenomenon? (2) How are these changes affecting end users, e.g., are the current digital
 140 map interfaces intuitive?

141 We investigated the impact of the European Digital Market Act (DMA)², an EU legislation
 142 aiming at preventing internet "gatekeepers" from exploiting dominant positions in the market.
 143 This legislation is intended to foster a fairer and more competitive digital environment. The
 144 "gatekeepers" affected by this legislation include major tech companies such as Amazon, Apple,
 145 Meta, Microsoft, and Alphabet, most of which are based in the United States. While DMA
 146 entered into force in November 2022, its effect on the "gatekeepers" has only recently become
 147 visible to consumers, starting in March 2024. DMA has a very substantial impact on digital
 148 maps. For instance, when comparing how location searches are handled on Google and Bing,
 149 Google Search no longer directly links to Google Maps. Instead, when using Bing to search
 150 for a location, Bing Maps is prominently displayed as the top result. Nonetheless, Microsoft
 151 has taken steps by enabling third-party web search applications through the Windows taskbar
 152 search box, allowing users to choose their preferred browser for displaying search results.

153 To answer our questions, we first define what *intuitiveness* means and conduct a binary
 154 scoring on 14 different map-based interfaces according to the following criteria:

- 155 1. *Map is shown directly (prominently), not as an advanced feature*: The map is directly
 156 accessible both for visualization and search without additional clicks.
- 157 2. *Map does not show irrelevant/surplus results*: The map does not show additional advert-
 158 isements that are outside the search temporal range or spatial extent.
- 159 3. *Map does not employ dark patterns*: E.g., if no results are shown, no relevant features
 160 exist in the map extent.
- 161 4. *Relevant information is shown with markers (e.g., price, rating)*: If appropriate, markers
 162 carry additional information relevant to the task at hand.
- 163 5. *Basemap options*: A basemap change (vector and satellite) or street view is available.
- 164 6. *Selection of possible map features on request*: E.g., clickable POIs are available for
 165 additional information.

166 To explain the criteria with concrete examples: If a map-based web-search interface
 167 displays the price of a hotel within the marker, as depicted in Figure 1a, we perceive this
 168 as more intuitive compared with an interface featuring generic or empty markers, as seen
 169 in Figure 1b. This is because the former reduces the number of clicks required to collect
 170 information for decision-making³. Conversely, if an interface prominently shows markers for
 171 irrelevant search results, such as hotels that are unavailable, we perceive it as unintuitive;
 172 see Figure 1b. By *dark patterns*, we refer to (map) design strategies that may mislead users,

² https://digital-markets-act.ec.europa.eu/index_en

³ Please note that we do not address issues of information overload here, as they did not occur in any of the tested interfaces.

(a) A query to Hotels.com (as of 04/24). (b) A query to Booking.com (as of 04/24).

■ **Figure 1** Two map interfaces for accommodations showing different types of markers.

■ **Table 1** Intuitiveness scores of map-based web search interfaces by indicator by example.

Indicator	Booking.com	Airbnb	Expedia	Hostelworld	Zillow	Trulia
Direct map display after a query	0	1	0	0	1	1
No irrelevant/surplus results	0	0	1	1	1	1
No dark patterns	0	0	1	1	1	1
Relevant information shown with markers	0	1	1	1	1	0
Basemap options	1	0	1	0	1	1
Selection of possible map features	0	1	0	0	0	0
Subtotal	16.7%	50.0%	66.7%	50.0%	83.3%	66.7%

173 force additional interaction steps (e.g., to display advertisements), lack transparency, and so
 174 on. It is important to note that this differs from omitting features or encountering technical
 175 limitations. We do *not* speculate whether these dark patterns have been intentionally
 176 deployed.

177 Overall, we examined 14 interfaces from 4 different sectors, namely travel, real estate, POI
 178 recommendations, and general-purpose web maps: (1) booking.com, hotels.com, expedia.com,
 179 hostelworld.com, airbnb.com, (2) zillow.com, trulia.com, immobilienscout24.at, immobili-
 180 enscout24.de, willhaben.at, (3) yelp.com, tripadvisor.com, and finally (4) maps.google.com,
 181 and maps.bing.com.

182 The interfaces have then been rated by 15 students (the authors of this paper) split into
 183 groups representing the aforementioned sectors. To test the map widgets, we performed a
 184 variety of queries depending on their intended use, e.g., searching for a hotel or vacation
 185 rental, asking for a restaurant nearby, searching for real estate and flats to rent, and so
 186 forth. Whenever possible, we explored multiple steps to arrive at the results. For instance,
 187 some interfaces offered AI-based chatbots for natural language interactions, and. In these
 188 cases, we compared the results from faceted search (e.g., number of rooms, city district,
 189 price range, features [e.g., garden]) versus a natural language query such as "Three rooms in
 190 Berlin for less than 650 Euro with a garden". To compare how map widgets have changed,
 191 we also compared current versions with past interface designs, e.g., via the Internet Archive's
 192 *Wayback Machine*⁴. Note that we are interested in comparing the *interaction*, not the results;
 193 e.g., different accommodation booking portals have overlapping (but not identical) offerings,
 194 real estate portals try to set themselves apart from the competition by offering unique
 195 features, etc.

⁴ <https://web.archive.org/>

196 **4 Results and Discussion**

197 Here, we discuss the results of our survey. Due to the limited space of a short paper, we
 198 focus on specific findings that provide good examples for the (un)intuitive interaction with
 199 map widgets. For instance, when querying a platform for accommodations, the resulting
 200 map behavior on some portals did not match our intuition; see Figure 2. While one could
 201 argue that the specific portal has limited the number of markers to prevent overcrowding,
 202 this was actually not the case, as a comparison between Figure 2a and Figure 2c reveals. It is
 203 unclear why zooming into specific (often previously marker-free) areas revealed new available
 204 hotels. Also, intuitively, the default behavior of a portal should be to show only available
 205 properties. Booking.com, however, was the only platform we tested that showed unavailable
 206 properties by default (forcing us to deselect this option manually for every new query). It
 207 is unclear what caused this behavior and why markers did not show up as expected. The
 208 list view of booking.com stated that "commission paid on bookings and other factors can
 209 affect property rankings.". We believe that such rankings may be more difficult to show on a
 210 map where all markers are visually equally prominent. It is also worth mentioning that this
 211 is not a technical limitation as other portals either group markers, e.g., Hotels.com, or the
 212 unexpected behavior or markers and otherwise missing results only occur at the edges of the
 213 map, e.g., Airbnb. Such cases are likely to be caused by underlying grids (not visible to the
 214 user).

(a) Query before zooming in (see the 6 markers at the top). (b) Close inspection of this area suddenly reveals 3 new hotels. (c) Markers without explicitly disabling unavailable properties.

■ **Figure 2** Changes to the map markers for the same query to booking.com while zooming and panning street by street.

215 Some platforms, such as the real estate portal Trulia or Redfin, have also recently removed
 216 previously available layers, e.g., crime data [2]. The argument brought forward here is that
 217 such crime data may lead to redlining and "reinforcing racial bias"⁵. In April 2024, Google
 218 and Apple removed a specific bus line (116) from their maps (and routing) in Barcelona
 219 following a request by the city council to prevent overcrowding⁶.

220 While these changes may be driven by a concern about the suggestiveness of spatial
 221 technologies, other cases are more difficult to explain despite the effectiveness of map-based
 222 web search. In Google, the tab "Maps" is no longer available. Moreover, when searching for
 223 a street, the interactive map a user would receive before is now a static Google Map *image*

⁵ <https://www.redfin.com/news/neighborhood-crime-data-doesnt-belong-on-real-estate-sites/>

⁶ <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2024/apr/16/barcelona-bus-route-removed-map-apps-tourist-overcrowding-park-guell>

224 of the region. Several real estate portals and digital marketplaces, such as Willhaben (shown
 225 in Figure 3a and Figure 3b), have removed their maps entirely, thereby severely hindering
 226 the search for rentals such as apartments in specific areas. Instead, one has to rely on the
 227 list view now, which leads to dozens more clicks. We initially expected privacy concerns, but
 228 this is not (only) the case, as clicking on a specific rental from the list now reveals the exact
 (or masked) location.

■ **Figure 3** Comparison between Willhaben.at real estate search in 2019 and 2024.

229 For immobilienScout24, another real estate portal, the functionality varies across regions.
 230 The German version includes a map and an experimental AI chatbot that translates real
 231 estate queries into facets. While the chatbot generally performs well, it struggles with
 232 districts and neighborhoods, which limits its effectiveness for spatial searches. In contrast,
 233 the Austrian version of the portal does not include a map. Additionally, some portals, like
 234 Expedia, offer a wide range of features, including loading Google Street View imagery for
 235 hotels of interest. More generally, these portals offer different search behavior depending on
 236 the region, such as the U.S. versus the EU.

238 5 Conclusions

239 The growing prominence of web maps has brought about a heightened awareness of privacy
 240 issues and data resale practices, raising questions about what actually drives the results
 241 being displayed on digital maps. Interestingly, for the first time in two decades, we see maps
 242 disappear, features being removed, or results displayed in a way that a naive user may no
 243 longer be able to explain. In this short paper, we reported on experiments surveying various
 244 known portals in markets such as real estate, accommodations, and POI recommendations.

245 We presented several cases by example that highlight issues of interest to our community:
 246 (1) Search results are (at least in parts) driven by commercial interests, and certain types
 247 of interfaces such as lists or AI-based chat-bots are more suitable to show selected results
 248 while hiding others or maximize the display of ads. Paradoxically, as map interfaces display
 249 information *effectively*, they may be less attractive for service providers such as real estate or
 250 travel portals. (2) While the literature has pointed out potential problems at the intersection
 251 of geo-technology and society before, current cultural and political trends are now resulting
 252 in service providers taking action, e.g., by removing data layers about neighborhood crime.
 253 Whether this is good or not remains to be discussed in future research. This also aligns
 254 with recent work on bias and debiasing in GeoAI. (3) Changes in legislation can lead to
 255 a radically different map experience across geographic regions, e.g., Google Maps and the
 256 way it integrates with Google Search in Europe is now reduced to mere *images of maps*,
 257 thereby drastically reducing usability compared to regions like the US. (4) Finally, rapid
 258 progress in natural language interfaces such as co-pilot (ChatGPT) has led to a situation

259 where web maps are de-emphasized simply because these systems cannot yet create or ingest
 260 web maps. For instance, Microsoft Bing now offers to answer questions such as "Good pizza
 261 restaurants nearby" via their AI Co-pilot. The results show (generated) textual descriptions
 262 (recommendations) and ranks for these places but also automatically load a map with data
 263 showing different places, leading to a confusing search experience. Geo-foundation models
 264 may change this in the future and bring map-based interactions to ChatGPT-like systems.
 265 However, there may still be ethical cartographic concerns, such as misleading information in
 266 AI-generated maps [8], which are applicable to web map design.

267 In the future, the described changes and dark patterns in map-based web search could
 268 also be studied using techniques such as eye-tracking [10]. Further research should also
 269 examine the growth of AI in map-based web search more closely.

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